

PREPARATION AND PROPERTY OF NANO-SiC_p/A356 COMPOSITES SYNTHESIZED WITH A NEW PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

Nano-SiC particles reinforced A356 aluminum alloy composites were prepared by molten-metal process, combined with high energy ball milling and ultrasonic vibration methods. The nano particles were β -SiC_p with an average diameter of 40nm, and pre-oxidized at about 850°C to form an oxide layer with thickness of approximately 4nm. The millimeter sized composite granules containing nano-SiC_p were firstly produced by milling the mixture of oxidized nano-SiC_p and pure Al powders, and then were remelted in the matrix-metal melt with mechanical stirring and treated by ultrasonic vibration to prepare the composite. The SEM analysis results show that SiC nanoparticles are dispersed well in the matrix and no serious agglomeration is observed. The tensile strength and elongation of the composites are increased with the increase of reinforcement fraction of SiC_p, and 2wt.% nano-SiC_p are improved by 19.5% and 43.5% respectively compared with the A356 alloy

1 INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) with ceramic particles as reinforcement have high specific strength, high specific stiffness, superior wear resistance, desirable thermal expansion and better dimensional stability than their matrix[1-4]. It is believed that MMCs with micron-scale particles would have low ductility, and nano-scale particles reinforced MMCs, termed as MMNCs, the ductility would be enhanced considerably even with a very low volume fraction of nano particles[5-7]. Hence MMNCs have gained widespread attention in scientific research and commercial application because of the demands for lightweight, high-modulus, and high-strength materials[7-10].

MMNCs are generally produced by two major methods, the solid state method and the liquid casting method. Usually the fabrication process of the solid state method has a high cost[7, 11, 12]. In the liquid method the way to produce MMNCs is economical, in which reinforced particles are added directly to liquid alloy by stirring and casting[13]. But the key issues during adding nano-sized ceramic particles into molten metal are wettability and dispersion. The wettability between nano-particles and the molten metal is very poor due to a much higher specific surface area for nano-particles. Therefore it is difficult to add nano-particles into molten metal with common stirring method. Solid-liquid mixed casting is a casting method in which alloy powders with good wettability are added to the melt with mechanical stirring to fabricate high alloy material ingots. This kind of method is proved to be feasible to fabricate MMCs by preparing composite granules which are made of ceramic particles and alloy powders with good wettability through mechanical alloying. Ceramic particles are considered as alloy element when the casting method is applied to the fabrication of MMCs[14] and the weight fraction of reinforcement could reach 5%[15] with micron-sized reinforcement. Su et al.[16] used aluminum powders as the carrier agent to fabricate 0.6%Al₂O₃/Al2024 composites. Mechanical alloying was achieved by ball-milling of which stearic acid was used as the process control agent(PCA) and resulted in composite granules with diameter

smaller than 100 μm . Then mechanical stirring, which is similar to the fabrication process of the composites reinforced by micron-sized particles, is used to add the composite granules to the melt and fine dispersion of Al_2O_3 particles was achieved. There is a problem when solid-liquid mixed castings works with MMNCs that the size of composite granules would decrease rapidly during the melting process of pure Al and traditional mechanical stirring is useless in dispersing particles in the melt uniformly on the macro level when the size of composite granules becomes too small. As a result, the content of reinforcement in MMNCs is limited and other new process for better dispersion is required.

In this work, Al MMNCs reinforced by dispersed SiC nanoparticles were fabricated by the process combined solid-liquid mixed casting and high-intensity ultrasonic vibration (UV). The mechanical alloying between SiC_p and pure Al powders was achieved by high energy ball-milling (HBM) without PCA. The millimeter sized composite granules, rather than micron-sized granules, were fabricated, and UV treatment was introduced to disperse the small agglomerations formed by the structures which exists due to the completely melting of composite granules. The microstructure and mechanical properties of $\text{SiC}_p/\text{A356}$ were also studied to understand the effect of nanoparticles in as-cast composites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The matrix material was A356 alloy, with compositions of 7%Si, 0.3%Mg, 0.19%Fe and balanced Al. The reinforcements were β -SiC particles with average diameter of 40nm. Pure aluminum powders for preparing composite granules had an average diameter of 30 μm . There were two main procedures of the experiment, HBM for fabrication of nano- SiC_p/Al composite granules and solid-liquid mixed casting to fabricate MMNCs.

The pretreatment of nano- SiC_p was calcination at 850 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 2h, removing the impurities and gas on the surface of nano- SiC_p and forming a compact oxidation film. Then nano-particles were mixed with pure Al powders with weight fraction of 6% to fabricate nano- SiC_p/Al composite granules by dry HBM without PCA. The mixture of nano- SiC_p and pure Al powders was milled in a QM-3SP4 planetary mill filled by stainless steel balls with diameter of 10mm at room temperature after the milling vessels was vacuumized. Rotation speed of the mill was kept about 150 rpm for 5h, 200 rpm for 15h and 300rpm for 5h. Ball-to-powder weight ratio was 5:1.

A balanced amount of Al-24.5Si, pure Al and pure Mg blocks were melted in a graphite crucible. The SiC_p/Al composite granules were preheated at 250 $^\circ\text{C}$ before adding into the melt. When the alloy was completely melted, the melt was cooled down to 680 $^\circ\text{C}$ and mechanical stirring was applied and preheated SiC_p/Al composite granules were added into the stirring vortex. The stirring speed was 250 rpm and the stirring was kept up for 10min after SiC_p/Al composite granules were added to the melt completely. When the stirring process was over, the melt was heated up to 720 $^\circ\text{C}$ and hold for 30min. In order to disperse SiC nano-particles in the melt, ultrasonic vibration with a 20 kHz, maximum 2.8 kW power output and a titanium alloy horn with 20 mm in diameter was introduced into the melt and kept for 3min. After ultrasonic vibration processing, the composite melt was cast into a permanent steel mould which was preheated to 250 $^\circ\text{C}$.

The tensile tests for unreinforced A356 and nanocomposites specimens were done with a SHIMATSU AG-IC100KN tester at strain rate of 1 mm/min at room temperature, and the diameter and gauge length of samples are 6 mm and 30 mm, respectively. The distribution of the SiC nanoparticles were investigated with a DMM-480C optical microscopy(OM), a JEOL JSM-7600F scanning electron microscopy (SEM), JEM2100(TEM). The samples were mechanical polished and etched using a solution with 0.5% vol. HF for 10 seconds.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructures of pretreated SiC_p

High temperature is required for the casting process of composite slurry during the stir-casting. But it would increase the possibility of the reaction between SiC_p and matrix aluminum to form Al_4C_3 , as shown in Fig. 1. It is known that mechanical properties of SiC will be degraded due to the formation of Al_4C_3 , and Al_4C_3 is unstable in some environments such as water, methanol, HCl, etc[17-18].

Fig. 1 SEM microstructures of nano-SiC_p/A356 composites with Al₄C₃ resulted from reaction of un-pretreated nano-SiC_p with Al melt

Fig. 2 Correlation of oxidation thickness and time of SiC_p during oxidation at 800, 850, 900°C

Artificial oxidation of SiC to produce a SiO₂ layer on the surface of SiC has been proven to be effective in preventing the reaction. Investigation on SiC_p oxidation at elevated temperatures shows that the oxidation increment of SiC_p, the dependence of the volume fraction and that of the thickness of SiO₂ layer on temperature are both parabolic[19]. Considering the SiC_p as regular spheres, the thickness of the SiO₂ layer defined as *d* could be estimated by Equations (1) and (2), where *R*₁ is the average radius of SiC_p before pretreatment, *R*₃ is the average radius of SiC_p after pretreatment, *R*₂ is the average radius of a hypothetic sphere formed by the remaining part of pre-treated spheres with the exception of the SiO₂ layer, *m* and *m'* are the weight of SiC_p before and after pretreatment respectively, and Δ*w*= *m'*-*m*, *d*=*R*₃-*R*₂.

$$\frac{V_{SiO_2}}{V_{SiC}} = \frac{\frac{4}{3}\pi(R_3^3 - R_2^3)}{\frac{4}{3}\pi(R_1^3 - R_2^3)} = \frac{\frac{3\Delta w}{\rho_{SiO_2}}}{\frac{2\Delta w}{\rho_{SiC}}} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{4}{3}\pi R_2^3 \rho_{SiC} + \frac{4}{3}\pi(R_3^3 - R_2^3)\rho_{SiO_2} = \frac{m'}{m} \frac{4}{3}\pi R_1^3 \rho_{SiC} \quad (2)$$

The density of β-SiC and amorphous state SiO₂ are 3.16g/cm³ and 2.196g/cm³ respectively. *R*₁, the average radius of nano-SiC_p, is 20nm. The thickness of pre-treated SiC_p under different pretreatment are shown in the curve of Fig. 2.

When the holding time is 2h at 850°C the thickness of SiO₂ layer is about 4nm, which is consistent with the result of TEM shown in Fig. 3b.

Fig. 3 TEM images of SiC_p after pretreatment at low (a) and high (b) magnification

3.2 Morphologies and microstructures of the SiC_p/Al composite granules

Fig. 4 shows the appearance of the composite granules which have an average diameter of 2mm. The ball milling was taken between ductile (pure Al powder) material and brittle material (nano-SiC_p particles) and consisted 3 stages[20]. In the first stage micro-forging existed between Al powders and grinding balls. The Al powders were broken into cakes and slices while the nano-SiC_p was stable on this ball milling condition. Then lamellar structure would be formed by the slice-shape Al and nano-SiC_p while the caky Al would be transformed and broken further. The distribution of SiC_p was concentrated on the junctions between two lamellar structures. The nano-SiC_p would adhere to the surfaces of the Al powders during the ball milling gradually in this stage. In the final stage microcosmic routes for diffusion would exist due to the crystal defects produced by plastic deformation and finally the mechanical alloying of nano-SiC_p and pure Al was achieved. At the same time repeated welding, fracturing and rewelding of lamellas structures would take place due to the heating effect and bending deformation brought by the plastic deformation.

Fig. 4 Morphologies of the composites granules with 6 wt.% nano-SiC_p

Compared with the long work period of mechanical alloying between Al and SiC_p, the welding of the Al lamellas conduct much more easily due to the high ductility of pure Al and large heating effect of plastic deformation. As a result that some SiC_p were captured by the composite granules in agglomerations, as shown in Fig. 5a. The dispersion of nano-SiC_p in the composite granules has significant influence on the dispersion and mechanical properties of the final MMNCs. When one-stage HBM were used to fabricate granules, serious agglomeration occurred in composite granules and could hardly be broken up by the UV process afterwards. To solve this problem a three-stages HBM process was chosen to make sure that the process of mechanical alloying and the welding of the Al lamellas complete respectively. The final SiC_p were dispersed uniformly in composite granules as shown in Fig. 5b.

Fig. 5 SEM microstructures of the composite granules:(a) one-stage HBM with 300rpm 15h, (b)three-stages HBM with 150rpm 5h, 200rpm 15h and 300 5h

3.3 Microstructure of the nano-SiC_p/A356 composites

After the composite granules added into the melt nano-SiC_p would diffuse in the melt along with the fusion of composite granules and mechanical stirring. But mechanical stirring would become incapable of dispersing the nanoparticles in the melt since the size of composite granules became smaller during the melting process. A kind of areas, as shown in Fig. 6, occur due to the pre-dispersion effect brought by the HBM. In this kind of areas the orientation and size of the crystalline grains were quite different from the others. The content of SiC_p was much higher and dispersed well in the areas. But the size of these areas were too small for the whole specimen and were considered as small agglomerations which might lead to the non-uniformity of MMNCs. UV process was taken to broken up these agglomerations by the combination of transient cavitations and acoustic streaming.

Fig. 6 Agglomeration block of nanocomposite without UV at low (a) and high (b) magnification

The dispersion of SiC nanoparticles of different weight percentage in the aluminum matrix was examined by SEM, as shown in Fig. 7. Microstructural studies conducted on the composites specimens show uniform distribution of SiC particles, and even the small agglomerations mentioned above could not be found in the samples containing different weight percentage of SiC nanoparticles.

Fig. 7 Microstructure of SiC_p/A356 with different reinforcement fraction (a)0.5wt% SiC_p/A356; (b) 1.0wt% SiC_p/A356;(c) 2wt% SiC_p/A356

It is generally recognized that most of SiC_p would be distributed in the eutectic region due to the low wettability between SiC_p and molten Al[21] except only a small part of SiC_p can be captured by the growing solid $\alpha\text{-Al}$ phase. As shown in Fig. 8a, SiC_p distributed in eutectic region spontaneously agglomerate into clusters of 100-200nm in size due to the long duration of the solidification of eutectic region. The size of the SiC_p clusters is acceptable and the distribution of SiC_p is fine as a whole. There are SiC_p in abundance distributed in $\alpha\text{-Al}$ are found. And this kind of distribution as shown in Fig. 8b may be attributed to the reaction between SiO_2 layer and $\alpha\text{-Al}$, and further research of TEM is required to confirm the interface combination status.

Fig. 8 SEM microstructures of MMNCs with UV:(a) eutectic region, (b) inner primary $\alpha\text{-Al}$ phase

3.4 Mechanical properties of the nano- $\text{SiC}_p/\text{A356}$ composites

The results of room temperature mechanical properties are given in Table 1. In order to make a comparison, the mechanical properties of the alloy only with ultrasonic processing are also listed in Table 1. It can be seen that SiC nanoparticles bring out good strengthening effects to aluminium alloy except 0.5% $\text{SiC}/\text{A356}$ due to the low content of reinforcement led to the non-uniformity of the MMNCs. For unreinforced A356 alloy with UV, the mechanical properties were also improved.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of $\text{SiC}_p/\text{A356}$ at room temperature

Materials	σ_b/MPa	$\delta/\%$
A356 alloy(without UV treatment)	189	3.9
A356 alloy	197	4.2
0.5% $\text{SiC}/\text{A356}$	200	5.0
1% $\text{SiC}/\text{A356}$	213	5.1
2% $\text{SiC}/\text{A356}$	226	5.5

As compared to the A356 aluminium alloy matrix, the tensile strength and elongation of the 2.0wt.% $\text{SiC}/\text{A356}$ nanocomposites were improved by 19.5% and 43.5% respectively in permanent mold casting. The higher tensile strength could be attributed to the fact that SiC particles act as obstacles to the motion of dislocation and good distribution of the nano- SiC particles and low degree of porosity lead to effective transfer of applied tensile load to the uniformly distributed SiC particulates. On the other hand, nano- SiC particles have grain-refined strengthening effect, which is improved with increasing weight fraction since they could hinder the growth of $\alpha\text{-Al}$ grains as shown in Fig. 9 clearly, and results in the increase of the tensile strength and ductility of MMNCs.

Fig. 9 Metallographic structures of A356 and SiC_p/A356 with different reinforcement fraction:
(a)A356 alloy; (b)0.5wt%SiC_p/A356; (c) 1.0wt% SiC_p/A356;(d) 2wt% SiC_p/A356

4 CONCLUSIONS

1. The millimeter sized composite granules containing nano-SiC_p were prepared by HBM, and can be used in a process of solid-liquid mixed casting to fabricate SiC_p/A356 composites. These composite granules with good wettability against Al alloy melt are considered as the carrier agent to make sure that nano-SiC_p could be added into Al alloy melt smoothly.
2. SiC nanoparticles are dispersed well in the matrix and no serious agglomeration is observed by cooperation of ultrasonic vibration process for the composite melt.
3. The tensile strength and elongation of the composites are increased with the increase of reinforcement fraction of SiC_p, and with 2wt.% nano-SiC_p they are improved by 19.5% and 43.5% respectively compared with the A356 alloy.

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